

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF AEROMAGNETIC ANOMALY MAP OF KOTON-KARFI (SHEET 227), NORTH-CENTRAL, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Aeromagnetic anomaly map of Koton-Karfi (Sheet 227) was profiled into 5 equal sections (North-South) for depth to base estimation employing Poorna C. Pal's mathematical modelling method. The anomaly map was sectioned into nine equal squares for brief spectral qualitative description. From the profiles it was observed that, depth-to-basement thickness of the sediments ranges between 600m and 1,100m increasing from south to north of the sheet. Qualitatively, the southern part of the area has high anomaly values and closely spaced which confirms the presence of iron ores while the northern region has low values of anomaly and are sparse due to the huge sediments brought in by Rivers Niger and Benue.

KEYWORDS: Aeromagnetic Anomaly, Koton-Karfi, Depth-to-Basement, Iron-Ore, Sediments

INTRODUCTION

Koton-Karfi and its environs is known for its iron mineralization, the reservoir potentials of the thick sediments can't be overlooked. The area of study covers the entire Sheet (Koton-Karfi, Sheet 227) and covers substantial part of Kogi State, with very small portion falling into the neighbouring Niger and Nasarawa States. It is located between latitudes 8°:00'N and 8°:30'N; and, longitudes 6°:30'E and 7°:00'E and covers a total area of 2,916km² (54km x 54km).

GEOLOGY

The study area occupies substantial part of Nupe Basin and shows the same geological setting. The principal litho-facies in the study area are sandstones which mostly strike N-S and have low dips. The basal lithology is usually the coarse pebbly sandstone with no lateral variation. Geometrically, the sand bodies are tabular to elongate and with some sand-bars, made up of multiple build-up of sand bodies (Adeleye, 1973). Structurally, the sediments bear the imprints of mild tectonism in form of low dips (less than 5°). The sandstones show planar bedding (mainly flat-lying) and there appears to be a little or no structural disturbance at the surface which is an indication of lack of apparent association with known tectonism. Several outcrops of the sandstones sections along the Lokoja - Abaji Road are preserved by a hard indurated top layer of laterite (Akanmu, 1998).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The Original map used was on a scale of 1:100,000 (Figure 1 is on a scale of 1:200,000) and it was sectioned into 6 equal squares for aerial spectral discussion. 5 nos. profiles were drawn starting up-north along latitude 8°:30'N at an interval of 7°:30' to the last one along latitude 8°:00'N down-south (Figures 2 - 6) and the anomaly along the profile are presented (Tables 1 - 5).

Poorna C. Pal's method of data analysis was employed. Poorna (1986) employs the mathematical manipulations (Figure 7) of the horizontal components of the minimum and maximum values the depth-to-basement. The method is a mathematical procedure and some parameters were obtained from the anomaly map (Nano-Tesla, NT) which was plotted against the distance (Olasehinde, 1990).

Figure 1. Aeromagnetic Map of the study Area.

Figure 2. Profile along Latitude $8^{\circ} 30'$ (00 km Southward)

Figure 3. Profile along Latitude $8^{\circ} 22.5'$ (13.50 km Southward)

Figure 4. Profile along Latitude $8^{\circ} 15'$ (27.00 km Southward)

Figure 5. Profile along Latitude $8^{\circ} 7.5'$ (40.50 km Southward)

Figure 6. Profile along Latitude $8^{\circ} 00'$ (54.00 km Southward)

RESULTS

The results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Comparison of Parameters and the Depth-to-Basement of the Profiles

Profile	Latitude	Dist (Southward) km	m nT	M nT	Xm (meters)	XM (meters)	H (meters)
1.	8 ^o 30.0'	00.00	7800	7850	6,300.00	5,700.00	1,086.00
2.	8 ^o 22.5'	13.50	7849	7891	4,500.00	3,900.00	909.00
3.	8 ^o 15.0'	27.00	7770	7840	3,300.00	3,900.00	840.00
4.	8 ^o 07.5'	40.50	7735	7770	3,300.00	2,700.00	768.00
5.	8 ^o 00.0'	54.00	7750	7885	3,150.00	2,700.00	657.00
Average			7781	7847	4110.00	3780.00	852.00

Table 2. Mathematical Relationships Used to Obtain the Various Values

m = Minimum Anomaly Value along the Profile
 M = Maximum Anomaly Value along the Profile
 X₀ = Epicentre (where X = X₀) = Av. Value = $\frac{(m+M)}{2}$ nT
 Xm = Horizontal distance of (m) from origin (meters)
 XM = Horizontal distance of (M) from origin (meters)
 U = $\sqrt{-(XmXM)}$ i)
 P = (Xm + XM)ii)
 θF = $\tan^{-1} \left(B \sqrt{\frac{U}{\pm F}} \right)$; where B is a constant = 1.1457iii)
 h = $\pm \frac{1}{2} ((P)\tan\theta F)$iv) Note: h is the depth-to-basement in meters

DISCUSSION

Qualitative Description

From the map of contours of total magnetic field intensity (Figure 1) southern part of the study area shows closely packed contours with an almost east-west trend, this, may not be unconnected with ironstones found in the southern part of the area. It also justifies the shallow depth-to-basement values. In the contrary, the anomaly map reveals a quiet and calm upper half where the contours are sparse. This confirms the high value of depth-to-basement due to huge deposits of sands from the activities of Rivers Niger and Benue.

Quantitative Analysis (Mathematical Modelling)

From the mathematical analysis of the obtained profiles, thicknesses ranging from 600m to 1,100m were obtained with a northward increment trend.

CONCLUSIONS

Values of the depth-to-basement corroborate the thickness of sediments of the area of study from previous geological information (mostly sedimentology) this shows that geophysical survey can deliver fast and reliable geological information; also Poorna C. Pal's method is easy and applicable for mathematical modelling of aeromagnetic anomaly maps.

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